

Linking Sediment Particle-Size Distributions to Pedological Variability: An Inferential Statistical Assessment in a Subtropical Watershed

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Abstract

The Chowfaldandi watershed in southern Bangladesh is a major tributary of the Matamuhuri River basin, delivering large sediment loads from upland terrains to the Bay of Bengal. Interactions between sediment particle-size distributions (PSD) and sediment physicochemical variability remain poorly quantified in this subtropical environment. To address this, we collected surface sediments (10-15 cm) at 10-km transects across three stations during the dry and wet seasons of 2022. PSD was measured following standard methods from the American Society for Testing and Materials, ASTM D422-63. Significant seasonal variations ($p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA) were observed in sediment particle-size fractions and physicochemical properties, including salinity (2–24 psu), particle density (2.45–2.67 g cm⁻³), and PO₄-P (4.13–8.96 μg kg⁻¹), with a clear seasonal predominance of very fine sand and silt particles. Pearson correlation and multiple linear regression models quantified PSD–sediment physicochemical interactions for medium and very fine silt in relation to NO₂-N concentration ($R^2 = 0.85–0.88$, $p < 0.01$). Fine sand proportion was strongly predicted by bulk density ($R^2 = 0.48$, $p < 0.05$). Fine and very fine clay content varied with NO₂-N and SiO₃-Si, respectively ($R^2 = 0.66–0.88$, $p < 0.05$), as well as with particle density and salinity ($p < 0.05$). Principal component analysis showed that PSD and sediment-bound nutrients account for 76.7% of the temporal variability. These findings reveal clear mechanistic links between particle-size distributions and sediment physicochemical variability, providing guidance for sediment management, nutrient-flux forecasting, and adaptive coastal planning in subtropical riverine systems.

Keywords: Particle-size distribution; Pedological variability; Statistical assessment; Nutrient-flux; Subtropical watershed.